

The detoxification potential of activated peat hydrosol towards cadmium ions

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To enhance the sorption capacity of soils incapable of retaining pollutants, materials with pronounced sorbent properties and high affinity for the soil environment are used [1]. A preparation based on activated peat hydrosol, produced by ultrasonic cavitation dispersion of peat raw material in an aqueous medium, can be considered as such a promising soil sorbent.

The aim of the study was to evaluate the sorption properties of activated peat and compare its efficacy with that of other materials (activated carbon and lignin) used as soil sorbents.

Sorption was carried out from model systems simulating soil solution (a 0.9% NaCl solution, the pH of which was adjusted to 6.7 using sodium bicarbonate).

As part of the study on the thermodynamic parameters of cadmium ion sorption by activated peat and the selected sorbents, sorption isotherms were constructed. The obtained data were processed using the Langmuir mathematical model. [2] The sorption capacity (a_m) of the activated peat hydrosol preparation, activated carbon, and lignin for Cd^{2+} was 151.5 mg/g, 111.1 mg/g, and 107.5 mg/g, respectively.

The kinetics of cadmium ion (Cd^{2+}) sorption on activated peat hydrosol and the comparison preparations were studied using the limited volume solution method with the construction of kinetic curves. The rate constant of the sorption process for the activated peat hydrosol preparation, activated carbon, and lignin was $1.7 \cdot 10^{-2} \text{ g} \cdot \text{mg}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1/2}$, $1.0 \cdot 10^{-3} \text{ g} \cdot \text{mg}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1/2}$, and $1.1 \cdot 10^{-4} \text{ g} \cdot \text{mg}^{-1} \cdot \text{min}^{-1/2}$, respectively.

Based on the results obtained, it can be concluded that preparations based on activated peat hydrosol have the highest sorption capacity for Cd^{2+} ions. Consequently, their application contributes to increasing the sorption capacity of soils and better "capturing" of soil pollutants, preventing their further movement through biosystems.

References:

1. Gorbunova N.S., Gromovik A.I., Cherepukhina I.V., Terentyeva Yu.Yu. // Sorption processes in soils. Issues of study and current state of the problem. 2021. Vol. 21. №. 2. Pp. 265-275.

2. Osipova E.A. // News of higher educational institutions. Chemistry and chemical technology. 2023. Vol. 6. №. 9. Pp. 65-70.